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ЙОДОДЕФИЦИТНЫЕ РАССТРОЙСТВА У НАСЕЛЕНИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ БЕЛАРУСЬ. УСЛОВИЯ И ФАКТОРЫ, СПОСОБСТВУЮЩИЕ ФОРМИРОВАНИЮ ЭНДЕМИЧЕСКОГО ЗОБА

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Аннотация: В работе проведен анализ информации о распространенности йододефицитных расстройств у населения Республики Беларусь, определение условий и факторов, способствующих формированию эндемического зоба. Показано, что самым распространенным и наиболее ранним проявлением хронической йодной недостаточности является увеличение размеров щитовидной железы или зоб. Выявлены причинные факторы и условия для возникновения йододефицитных заболеваний. Доказано, что основной причиной возникновения йододефицитных заболеваний является недостаточное поступление йода из внешней среды в организм человека и животных.

Ключевые слова: йододефицитные расстройства, эндемический зоб

IODINE DEFICIENCY FRUSTRATION AT THE POPULATION OF REPUBLIC OF BELARUS. THE CONDITIONS AND FACTORS PROMOTING FORMING OF THE LOCAL CRAW

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Annotation: In work the analysis of information on prevalence of iodine deficiency frustration at the population of Republic of Belarus, definition of the conditions and factors promoting forming of a local craw is carried out. It is shown that the most widespread and earliest manifestation of chronic iodic insufficiency is increase in the sizes of a thyroid gland or a craw. Causative factors and conditions for developing of iodine deficiency diseases are revealed. It is proved that insufficient intake of iodine from external environment in a human body and animals is a basic reason of developing of iodine deficiency diseases.

Keywords: iodine deficiency frustration, endemic craw

Relevance. Despite resuming of mass iodic prevention, iodine deficiency frustration remain a current medical and social problem in connection with their prevalence with people of any age. About 2 billion inhabitants of Earth live in the territories, which are grown poor by the content of iodine, over 700 million people, have an enlargement of the thyroid gland (a local craw), 43 million suffer from the mental retardation which developed as a result of iodic insufficiency [1]. At the children born in the conditions of iodic deficiency, the coefficient of intellectual development is 10-15 points lower, than at their peers from iodoprovided areas. The iodine deficiency diseases which are formed on this background are an important medico-social and economic problem since they are followed by disturbances of structure and function of a thyroid gland and also lead to disturbances of fertility, forming of congenital anomalies of development, growth of perinatal and child mortality, significant decrease in intellectual, educational and professional potential of the nation [2].

The problem of iodic insufficiency is relevant for our country that is confirmed by existence of almost universal geophysical iodine deficiency in soils and waters of Belarus. Iodine content is in soils ranging from 0.64 up to 9.23 mg/kg, natural meadow vegetation has from 0.10 to 0.49 mg/kg of iodine, depending on the soil. In water, concentration of iodine is also insignificant, in the north of the republic – 3.2 mkg/dm³, in the center – 2.7 mkg/dm³, in the south – 1.9 mkg/dm³. Therefore at the initiative of the Ministry of Health events for fight against iodine deficiency diseases in Republic of Belarus are held. Does not raise doubts that the iodine deficiency in the environment and in food stuffs has negative impact on health of the population and, first of all, on

the most vulnerable groups – children, teenagers, pregnant women and the feeding women.

Purpose. The analysis of information on prevalence of iodine deficiency frustration at the population of Republic of Belarus, definition of the conditions and factors promoting forming of a local craw.

Materials and methods of a research. In work comparative and estimated and analytical methods for the studying of data of the Ministry of Health of Republic of Belarus and National statistical committee and provided to literary and Internet sources of materials are used. The received results are processed statistically by a package of standard statistical programs.

Results and their discussion. It is established that insufficient intake of iodine in an organism leads to expansion of a chain of the consecutive adaptive processes directed to maintenance of normal synthesis and secretion of hormones of a thyroid gland. If the iodine deficiency remains for a long time, there is a failure of mechanisms of adaptation to the subsequent development of iodine deficiency pathology.

It is shown that the most widespread and earliest manifestation of chronic iodic insufficiency is increase in the sizes of a thyroid gland or a craw. At a moderate iodine deficiency and sufficient compensation of thyroid function, the craw without dysfunction of a thyroid gland can be the only clinical manifestation of iodic deficiency [3]. At increase of degree of iodic deficiency against the background of a goitrous endemia there is a dysfunction of a thyroid gland – the deficiency of thyroid hormones develops, the manifest hypothyroidism having characteristic clinical signs is formed subclinical and further.

The following iodine deficiency frustration (diseases) of the population of Republic of Belarus are registered:

- simple non-toxic craw (local craw);
- nodal non-toxic craw;
- hypothyroidism;
- local cretinism;
- toxic adenoma of a thyroid gland [4].

It is revealed that causative factors and conditions for developing of iodine deficiency diseases are:

- insufficient intake of iodine in an organism owing to its low contents in food stuffs (water);
- disturbance of absorption of iodine in digestive tract;
- disturbance of processes of digestion of iodine thyroid gland, genetic-sky defects of biosynthesis of thyroid hormones;

- deficiency in the environment and food stuffs of zinc, bromine, molybdenum, selenium and excess of calcium, fluorine, chrome, manganese;
- existence in the environment of the "goitrogenic" factors capable to influence structure of a thyroid gland;
- consumption of goitrogenic food stuffs;
- medicines: streptomycin, streptocides, antibiotics (benzylpenicillin, erythromycin, etc.), threostatik – derivative thioureas, perchlorates, lithium salts, Amiodaronum;
- the physiological states connected with the increased need for iodine [5].

It is proved that insufficient intake of iodine from external environment in a human body and animals is a basic reason of developing of iodine deficiency diseases. Iodine – the essential microelement having important biological value since is a component of molecules of the hormones of a thyroid gland (thyroxine, triiodothyronine) rendering specific biological effect.

The significant contribution to forming of iodine deficiency states is made by disturbance of providing with selenium. It is caused, first, by influence of selenium on metabolism of thyroid hormones and, secondly, the proved deficiency of selenium in soils of Belarus [6]. It is proved that characteristic feature of the goitrous endemia arising at a combination of low sizes of iodine and selenium is the imbalance of thyroid hormones: accumulation of thyroxine with parallel decrease in sizes of triiodothyronine and aggravation of the phenomena of a hypothyroidism.

Among the conditions, promoting action of a causative factor and development of a disease the extreme importance of intoxications of various origin is revealed. These intoxications can be connected with bad sanitary and hygienic conditions, with bad quality of drinking water, with the irrational and monotonous food poor in vitamins or rich with goitrogens (for example, in cabbage, turnip, swede, soy, etc.) and some substances necessary for an organism, and, at last, with infectious diseases.

It is established that the disease is promoted by the changes in an organism connected with the puberty period; at the same time more often the disease develops at a female part of the population in connection with features of the hormonal status. After 20–30 the probability of a disease decreases, especially at men.

Conclusions. Thus, knowledge of factors and conditions of developing of a local craw gives the chance of performing timely prevention of a local craw, and as a result decrease in incidence on this pathology.

Список литературы

[1] Данилова Л.И. Болезни щитовидной железы и ассоциирование с ними заболевания. / Л. И. Данилова. – Минск: Нагасаки: [б. и.], 2005. 470 с.

[2] Базарбекова Р.М. Особенности здоровья беременных и детей раннего возраста в очаге зобной эндемии: автореф. дис. ... д-ра мед. наук : 14.00.09. / Р.М. Базарбекова. – Алматы, 1996. 49 с.

[3] Дедов И.И. Эндокринология: учебник для студентов медицинских вузов. / И.И. Дедов, Г.А. Мельниченко, В.В. Фадеев. – Москва: ГЭОТАР – Медиа, 2007. 432 с.

[4] Забаровская З.В. Заболевания щитовидной железы, обусловленные дефицитом йода: учеб.-метод. Пособие. / З.В. Забаровская, Т.В. Мохорт, А.П. Шепелькевич; Белорус. гос. мед. ун-т, 1-я каф. внутр. болезней. – Минск: БГМУ, 2007. [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <http://rep.bsmu.by/handle/BSMU/5164>. (дата обращения: 21.03.2021).

[5] Микроэлементозы человека: этиология, классификация, органопатология. / А.П. Авцын и др. – М.: Медицина, 1991. 496 с.

[6] Гресь Н.А. Биоэлементный статус населения Беларуси: экологические, физиологические и патологические аспекты. / Н.А. Гресь, А.В. Скальный. – Минск: Харвест, 2011. 352 с.

Bibliography (Transliterated)

[1] Danilova L.I. Diseases of the thyroid gland and associated diseases. / L.I. Danilova. – Minsk: Nagasaki: [b. and.], 2005. 470 p.

[2] Bazarbekova R.M. Health features of pregnant women and young children in the focus of goiter endemic: author. dis. ... Dr. med. Sciences: 14.00.09. / R.M. Bazarbekov. – Almaty, 1996. 49 p.

[3] Dedov I.I. Endocrinology: a textbook for medical students. / I.I. Dedov, G.A. Melnichenko, V.V. Fadeev. – Moscow: GEOTAR – Media, 2007. 432 p.

[4] Zabarovskaya Z.V. Diseases of the thyroid gland caused by iodine deficiency: study guide. Benefit. / Z.V. Zabarovskaya, T.V. Mohort, A.P. Shepelkevich; Belarusian. state honey. un-t, 1st department. int. diseases. –

Minsk: BSMU, 2007. [Electronic resource]. – URL: <http://rep.bsmu.by/handle/BSMU/5164>. (date of access: 03/21/2021).

[5] Human microelementosis: etiology, classification, organopathology. / A.P. Avtsyn et al. – M.: Medicine, 1991. 496 p.

[6] Gres N.A. Bioelement status of the population of Belarus: ecological, physiological and pathological aspects. / ON THE. Gres, A.V. Rocky. – Minsk: Harvest, 2011. 352 p.

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